

D4.3 – Lunar Water Ice Simulant

prepared for

WP4.2 – Lunar Raw Water and Ice Simulant Development

Version: 1.0

Published: 2024-07-06

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Funded by
the European Union

Document Change Log:

Version	Date	Author name(s)	Description of Change
1.0	2024-07-06	P. Zabel	

1 Lunar Water Ice Simulant

NOTE: A detailed description of the development process and the decisions made that resulted in the final water ice simulant can be found in deliverable D4.4 Simulant Development Report.

The lunar water ice simulant for LUXEX was developed using the heritage of TUBS with such processes. To produce the ice, deionized water is used to avoid mineral or other contaminants.

The ice is then mixed with pre-cooled regolith to produce an icy-regolith simulant.

The ice is produced on-demand in the laboratories of TUBS for each experiment run. For the complete LUXEX validation test campaign several kilograms of this simulant have been produced.

Figure 1-1: Cryo-SEM image of desiccated water ice particles with spherical shape.

Figure 1-2: Images of dried water ice samples.